

EarthCube GeoCODES

Data Plus X Towards a Geoscience Scientific Gateway

Kenton McHenry, Mike Bobak, Kevin Coakley, Doug Fils, Lisa Gatzke, Steve Richard, Dave Valentine, Ilya Zaslavsky, Bing Zhang, Christine Kirkpatrick

University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, University of California San Diego, U.S. Geoscience Network, Ocean Leadership
mchenry@illinois.edu

ABSTRACT

The NSF EarthCube program has worked to bring together data repositories within the geosciences in the adoption of schema.org to annotate stored datasets and allow them to be crawlable. Through this, data stored within the union of these repositories can be indexed centrally by resources such as Google or other services perhaps more tuned for geoscience or a particular area within it. We will present an effort by the past two EarthCube offices, GeoCODES [1], to prototype such a service. In addition to crawling, indexing, and presenting datasets within a unified search interface the effort aims to provide additional capabilities along the gateway notion allowing users of the system to better make use of the data. One such aspect is that of bringing together the tools catalogued within the EarthCube Resource Registry so that they are discoverable along with the datasets that they are capable of operating on. This is being extended further to allow notebooks collected from the community through the annual call for notebooks [2] or elsewhere to also be associated with datasets and even executed from the results page interface through MyBinder or Google Colab with the retrieved data already pre-loaded. Further, given the growing realization in the importance of addressing how users interact and effectively make use of software tools we will present on our interactions with a professional user interface/user experience (UI/UX) team and the aims there in terms of determining layout improvements. Overall, we will describe and demonstrate GeoCODES [3] in the context of a possible scientific gateway providing capabilities on top of the data as described, as well as other capabilities determined important from the geoscience community such as identifying related datasets, and temporal and geospatial search.

Keywords—*geoscience, data repositories, discoverability, data analysis*

REFERENCES

- [1] EarthCube GeoCODES, <https://www.earthcube.org/geocodes>
- [2] EarthCube Call for Notebooks, <https://www.earthcube.org/notebooks>
- [3] GeoCODES Demonstration Site, <https://geocodes.earthcube.org>

The screenshot displays the GeoCODES web interface. The top navigation bar includes the EarthCube logo, the GeoCODES name, and links for SPARQL and About. The main header features the GeoCODES logo and a search bar containing the term 'hydrology'. Below the search bar, there are radio buttons for 'All', 'Tool', and 'Data', with 'All' selected. A sidebar on the left lists filter categories: Resource Type (with counts for data: 385, researchProject: 23, tool: 1), Keywords, Place, Publisher/Repo, and Year Published, along with a Feedback button. The main content area shows search results for 'hydrology', indicating 409 selected of 409 results. The first result is titled 'ANTAEM project airborne EM resistivity data from McMurdo Region' and includes an abstract, keywords, and a data link. The second result is 'CFC analyses of Lake Kivu (Rwanda) water. Mixolimnion.' with its own abstract and description.

Version: 0.9.0 Date: 2021-06-14

Version: 0.9.0 Date: 2021-06-14